

ISic0265

I.Sicily inscription 0265

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. L(ucius) · Baebius · L(uci) f(ilius)
2. Gal(eria) · Iuncinus
3. praef(ectus) · fabr(um) praef(ectus)
4. coh(ortis) IIII · Raetorum
5. trib(unus) · milit(um) · leg(ionis) · XXII
6. Deiotariana
7. praef(ectus) · alae · Astyrum
8. praef(ectus) · vehiculorum
9. iuridicus · Aegypti

Apparatus

Text based upon Bitto 2001

Translation (en)

Lucius Baebius Iuncinus, son of Lucius, of tribe Galeria, praefectus fabrum, prefect of the 4th Cohort of Raeti, military tribune of the 22nd Legion of Deitarus, prefect of Ala Astyrum, praefectus vehiculorum, justice-officer of Egypt

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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Bibliography

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